

M_t or not M_t: Temporal variation in detection probability in spatial capture-recapture and occupancy models

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Appendix 1: Input parameters for simulation scenarios

Spatial capture-recapture

All scenarios:

Abundance $N=60$

Number of detectors $J=56$, spaced 100 units

$K=8$ sampling occasions

Scale parameter of the half-normal detection function $\sigma = 80$

Scenario 1: temporal variation in p_0 is constant across detectors

$$\text{logit}(p_{0,k}) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Z_k$$

$$Z = \{0, 1, \dots, K - 1\}$$

$$\alpha_0 = -2.1$$

$$\alpha_1 = -0.3$$

Scenario 2: p_0 varies spatially and temporally

$$\text{logit}(p_{0,jk}) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Z_{jk}$$

$$\alpha_0 = -3.2$$

$$\alpha_1 = -0.8$$

$$Z_{jk} \sim \text{Normal}(\mu_{Z,j}, 0.5)$$

$$\mu_{Z,j} \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)$$

Scenario 3: p_0 varies spatially and temporally, is correlated with density covariate X

$$\text{logit}(p_{0,jk}) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Z_{jk}$$

$$\alpha_0 = -3.2$$

$$\alpha_1 = -0.8$$

$$Z_{jk} \sim \text{Normal}(\mu_{z,j}, 0.5)$$

$$\mu_{z,j} \sim \text{Normal}(\bar{X}_j, 0.5)$$

\bar{X}_j = mean of density covariate X in 4 grid cells surrounding detector j (detectors sit at the intersection of grid cells)

Scenario 2a: Degree of temporal variation in p_0 differs by detector

$$\text{logit}(p_{0,jk}) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Z_{jk}$$

$$\alpha_0 = -3.2$$

$$\alpha_1 = -0.7$$

$$\mu_{z,j} \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)$$

$$\sigma = \{0.2, 0.5, 1, 1.2\}$$

$$u_j \sim \text{cat}(\pi = \{0.25, 0.25, 0.25, 0.25\})$$

$$Z_{jk} \sim \text{Normal}(\mu_{z,j}, \sigma_{u[j]})$$

Parameters above are for the ‘base’ scenario 2a; for the version of the scenario where p_0 varies, on average, 10-fold, $\sigma = \{0.2, 0.5, 1, 1.5\}$ and $\alpha_1 = -0.8$.

Scenario 2b: Skew of temporal variation in p_0 differs by detector

$$\text{logit}(p_{0,jk}) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Z_{jk}$$

$$\alpha_0 = -3.2$$

$$\alpha_1 = -0.7$$

$$\mu_{z,j} \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)$$

$$\gamma = \{-10, -2, 0, 2, 10\}$$

$$u_j \sim \text{cat}(\pi = \{0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2\})$$

$$Z_{jk} \sim \text{skew Normal}(\mu_{z,j}, 1, \gamma_{u[j]})^*$$

* Generated with function `rsn(n, xi=location (μ), omega=scale (1), alpha=shape (γ))` in R package `sn v.2.1.0` (Azzalini, 2022)

Scenario 2c: Detector level variation in p_0 is temporally correlated

$$\text{logit}(p_{0,jk}) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Z_{jk}$$

$$\alpha_0 = -3.2$$

$$\alpha_1 = -0.8$$

$$\mu_{z,j} \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)$$

$$u_{jk} \sim \text{Normal}(\mu_{z,j}, 1)$$

$$\mathbf{Z}_j = \mathbf{u}_j \mathbf{L}$$

Where \mathbf{L} is the transpose of the Cholesky factor of correlation matrix $\mathbf{\Sigma}$, with dimensions $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, K$ and entries $\sigma_{i,j} = \exp(\frac{|i-j|}{3})$

Occupancy

All scenarios:

Number of detectors $J=100$

$K=8$ sampling occasions

Note: '6-fold' and '3-fold' in the tables below refers to the average ratio of maximum to minimum detection probability at a sampling location over sampling occasions.

Scenario 1: variation in p is constant across detectors

$$\text{logit}(p_k) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Z_k$$

$$Z = \{0, 1, \dots, K - 1\}$$

Parameter	6-fold	3-fold
α_0	-1	-1.38
α_1	-0.3	-0.18

Scenario 2: p varies spatially and temporally

$$\text{logit}(p_{jk}) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Z_{jk}$$

Parameter	6-fold	3-fold
α_0	-1.95	-1.8
α_1	-0.78	-0.9

$$Z_{jk} \sim \text{Normal}(\mu_{z,j}, 0.5)$$

$$\mu_{z,j} \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)$$

Scenario 3: p varies spatially and temporally, is correlated with occupancy covariate X

$$\text{logit}(p_{jk}) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Z_{jk}$$

Parameter	6-fold	3-fold
α_0	-1.95	-1.8
α_1	-0.78	-0.9

$$Z_{jk} \sim \text{Normal}(\mu_{z,j}, 0.5)$$

$$\mu_{z,j} \sim \text{Normal}(X_j, 0.5)$$

X_j = value of occupancy covariate X at detector j

References:

Azzalini, A. (2022). The R package 'sn': The Skew-Normal and Related Distributions such as the Skew-t and the SUN (version 2.1.0). URL <http://azzalini.stat.unipd.it/SN/>, <https://cran.r-project.org/package=sn>